

3D THERMO-MECHANICAL MODEL BASED SIMULATION OF THE WELDING OF THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITE TAPE USING AUTOMATED TAPE LAYING (ATL) PROCESS

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ABSTRACT

The present paper describes the current state of works done during the STELLAR project about the ATP simulation. To assess the welding quality of the thermoplastic taps, the computations of the contact pressure, the temperature and the phase evolution in the matrix (evolution the degree of crystallinity) are in first importance. In the present paper, we describes two approaches to solve the 3D thermo-mechanical problem: the first one corresponds to a steady state assumption solved with an implicit scheme and the second one corresponds to the dynamical problem taking into account of the kinematic of the tool, and solved with an explicit scheme.

1 INTRODUCTION

Driven by the future environmental standards, transport industries look for CO₂ impact reduction of theirs vehicles. The aim of STELLAR project is to develop the manufacturing process for high-speed placement of fibre reinforced matrices, in selected locations of a composite structure and to provide the optimum reinforcement, weight and cost profile within a part. The global project focuses on the Automated Tape Laying (ATL) process to selectively place reinforced thermoplastic tapes following 3 manufacturing routes: selective reinforcement of existing components; direct additive manufacture of components; manufacture of selectively reinforced tailored blanks for compression moulding.

In the ATL process as sketched in Figure 1, a tape is placed and progressively welded on the substrate [1], [2], [3], [4]. By laying additional layers in different directions, a part with desired properties and geometry can be produced. However, the welding of the layers requires physical conditions, and most important among them is the permanent contact and the temperature required to ensure there is diffusion between the macromolecules. Moreover, precise diffusion of the macro-molecules through the welded interface, which characterizes a correct welding quality, takes time. This is a crucial question to increase the speed of the process. Due to low thermal conductivity of thermoplastics, higher temperatures can be reached at the interface with local heating.

One of the objectives of the project is to enhance the modelling tools to support the development of these technologies [5], [6], [7], [8]. Based on the experience in the welding simulation of metallic parts [9], in composite manufacturing simulation with complex kinematic tools [10] and in thermo-forming [11], ESI Group works to model these complicated tasks. These ESI developed models will include the kinematics of the tape-laying, simulation of the heating of the tape, a thermo-kinetic module, compaction, bonding and finally a residual stress evaluation. The present paper will describe the current state of described developments for the ATL simulation with the help of a 3D thermo-mechanical model.

To assess the welding quality of the thermoplastic tapes, the computations of the contact pressure, the temperature and the phase evolution in the matrix (evolution of the degree of crystallinity) are of at most importance. The material transformations as the degree of crystallinity are not described in this paper, but on-going work is carried out to adapt the metal library of SYSWELD to thermoplastic

material. In the present paper, we describes two approaches to solve the thermo-mechanical problem: the first one corresponds to a steady state assumption solved with an implicit scheme and the second one corresponds to the dynamical problem taking into account the kinematics of the tool, and then solved with an explicit scheme.

Figure 1: Sketch of the Automatic tape placement process

2 STEADY STATE ANALYSIS

In the cases where the tool moves with a constant velocity and the part has a simple geometry, some simplifications can be made to consider for a steady state approach. In theory, steady-state conditions exist for components presenting an “infinite” length in the direction of the motion. However from experience, it shows that this approach could be a good estimation when the velocity of the tool and the geometry of the part are constant during a large enough welding time.

The problem is then solved in an Eulerian frame: instead of considering a moving tool with time dependent boundary conditions, the problem is solved in a frame attached to the tool. In other words, the heating source and the roller are fixed, while the material is assumed to move with a constant velocity ‘V’ in the opposite direction to the one in which the roller move. Once the simulation done, the temperature or the pressure history of an actual material point can easily be assessed in post-treatment, by following a moving point with velocity V along a streamline representing the actual material trajectory [9], [12].

In the present approach, the mechanical analysis and the thermal analysis have been done in two separated phases. First the mechanical computation is done in order to assess both the pressure contact imposed by the roller on the tape and the deformation of the roller. Then the thermal computation is done. In the case where the roller is made with soft material like a silicone, the thermal simulation is carried out with the deformed geometry of the roller, obtained from the mechanical simulation.

2.1 Mechanical analysis

The inertial effect, as the volume forces are neglected. The equilibrium equation (1) is then given as follows:

$$\text{div } \sigma = 0 \quad (1)$$

The frictions between the various parts are also neglected. Thus the differential velocity between the tool, the tape and the support parts isn’t taken into account. So the simulation is reduced to a compact model, where the velocity V is zero. The problem is therefore solved with an implicit scheme using the ESI’s IMPLICIT Solver.

Lagrangian contact type 54 is used to define the contact interfaces between the various parts.

Figure 2: Mechanical model of the steady state model

Figure 3: Displacement contour after compaction – steady state mechanical model

2.2 Thermal analysis

In the present approach, the problem is a diffusion-convection problem and therefore differential equation (2) must integrate a supplementary transfer term before solving:

$$\rho C \left(\frac{\partial \theta}{\partial t} + V \cdot \text{grad } \theta \right) - \text{div}(\lambda \cdot \text{grad } \theta) - Q = 0 \quad (2)$$

In the above equation, θ is the temperature, ρ is the density, C is the specific heat, V is the velocity of the tool, λ is the conductivity tensor and Q represents the heat source distribution.

This approach is based on the work previously made by ESI for the simulation of the welding of metal parts with the SYSWELD solver [9], [13]. The method used in SYSWELD to solve these problems is based on a streamline upwind technique, which eliminates the oscillations that are normally

encountered with this type of systems, where high Peclet numbers occurs ($Pe = \rho CV \Delta x / \lambda$, Δx being the mesh size).

The approach implemented in SYSWELD can deal with a uniform translator, circular or helical motion. However, as the solver is for now dedicated to the metal parts, only isotropic thermal properties are available for now.

2.3 example and results

In the example shown in Figure 2, the roller is made of silicone, a highly deformable material. The roller and the tap are meshed in 3D, while the support is meshed in 2D. In a first approach, the material used for the roller is a simple elastic model with a Young modulus of 10 MPa and a Poisson's coefficient of 0.495 (it is known that it is not advised to put 0.5 for a Poisson's coefficient in FE simulation). The material used for the tap is an orthotropic 3D model dedicated to composites materials in ESI implicit scheme.

To decrease the size of the problem in this feasibility phase, only a quarter of the roller has been used for the purpose of simulation. Again only half portions of the tape and the support have been used for modelling (Figure 2). The symmetries are taken into account via the boundary conditions. In that way, the displacements are blocked in the y direction along the plan of symmetry (xz). The second plan of symmetry of the roller is the plan (xy), passing through the centre of the roller. This symmetry (xy) don't really existed in reality, but able a decrease in the size of the model. Consequently, the roller global behaviour will be a little stiffer than reality. Furthermore, it has to be noticed that this plan moves during the simulation with the compression of the roller onto the tape. To apply the symmetry condition, the nodes belonging to this plan (xy) are constrained by the displacement of a master node in the z direction. In that way, all these nodes have the same z-displacement. The compaction force is then applied to the master node in the z-direction. A tension force is also applied to the first extremity of the tap (to simulate the tension applied by the feeding system), while the displacements of the other extremity are blocked to simulate the bonding of these nodes to the support. The model has been meshed with 30,000 elements and the size of the elements near the contact zones is of an order of 0.5.

Figure 3 shows the displacement in the deformed state and the Figure 4 shows the contact pressure results. The contact pressure has been drawn along two paths: one along a node that is streamlined in the longitudinal direction of the UD and another in the transversal direction. The continuous green lines represent the raw results. It can be seen that the results are a little scattered. It's typical with the punctual contact which are usually used in the industrial software [14], [15]. Integral contact methods like the mortar method could obtained smoother results as shown in [14], [15], but their CPU costs limit them to academic cases for the moment. Intermediate method like the smooth contact element [16] is available in ESI's Solver. In this method, the master surface is smoothed by interpolation before applying the contact itself. Good results could be obtained with this one and it will be tested in future works. The dotted blue lines represent filtered results obtained with the filter BW100 of VISUAL ENVIRONNEMENT. These lines fit well the results and are exempted of the scattering. It can be seen that the pressure is already applied on the tape before the tape passes under the roller. After the roller, the pressure comes back to zero as there is no more contact. Because of the possible mismatch of the thermal expansion at the interface during the healing phase (and other mechanical mismatches), residual stress can occur [17]. Thus, while the pressure contact is zero, the expected calculated stress in the tape after healing should not be zero. However, the healing phase is not taken into account in this model. Furthermore, a great increase in pressure can be seen from the transversal raw curve, at the edge side of the tape. However, this increase could be explained by the transversal behavior of the modelled tape, which is stiff comparison to reality, as it isn't taking into account of the melted phase of the resin but the solid one. In the same way, only one row of linear elements is used in the UD thickness for model size consideration, as it is a feasibility phase. However this also increases the stiffness of the tape.

Figure 4: Pressure contact contour (left) and plots along profile curves (right) after compaction – steady state mechanical model

Based on the deformed geometry obtained from the mechanical simulation, a thermal model has been made. The support part is heated in front of the tape with standard heating source functionality available in the SYSWELD library. These pre-defined heating sources are initially designed for metal welding process. A work to adapt them to the present process will have to be made in future works. Thermal contact resistances have been defined between the support and the tap, as between the tap and the roller, in order that heat flux exchanges can be made between the parts. The temperature field is shown in Figure 5 (the roller part has been hidden in this image). The displayed temperatures are high because of the default values used for the heating source, fitted for metal welding.

Figure 5: Temperature contour results obtained with a pre-defined heating source from the SYSWELD library (initially dedicated to metal welding) – Thermal steady state model

3 EXPLICIT THERMO-MECHANICAL ANALYSIS WITH TOOL KINEMATICS

In the case where the kinematics of the tool cannot be reduced to a steady-state, the previous approach is not available anymore. There are various cases where the steady-state assumption is not valid and they are:

- With a change of velocity of the tool.
- With a more complex path than a long translation, circular or helical path.
- When the effect of steering and wrinkling are studying.
- In the case of multi-deposition of tapes with a short time between each pass, meaning that the previous added heat flux is not vanished before the new pass of the tool.
- Etc.

In that case, an explicit scheme can be more appropriate to take into account the various kinematics and the time dependent effects during modelling. The coupled thermo-mechanical problem is solved in the same time with the ESI's PAM-FORM 2015 Solver.

For time CPU optimization, the composite tape is modelled with shell elements. The material used here for the composite tape is material 140, which is a material dedicated to composites in the forming simulation when using PAM-FORM. It is an orthotropic material which can handle the fabric and the UD reinforcements. The only difference between these two modes is the second fibre direction computation. For fabric, the fibre directions follow the deformation of the elements whereas the UD mode assumes that the second fibre direction remains orthogonal to the first fibre direction [11]. This material model is a non-linear elasto-plastic material for which temperature, strain rate and curvature dependency can be added. There is also a damage behaviour option, but for now it is not relevant in this process model. The following behaviour is defined through the material input:

- Tension and compression deformation in fibre directions.
- In-plane shear deformation.
- Bending deformation in fibre directions.
- Thickness deformation through normal pressure.

In PAM-FORM 2015, it is possible to use look-up tables to define material input. Look-up tables allow introducing of dependency for the material parameters. This new feature will simplify a lot the material characterization of the material.

3.1 Laying of one tape

The deposition of one tape is decomposed in 2 phases:

- The first one is closed to the steady-state case: in one hand, a force is applied to the roller to put it on compression onto the tape and the support; and in second hand, a tension is applied to the tap.
- The second phase corresponds to the deposition itself and takes into account of the kinematic of the tool.

In this early study, the kinematic is simple and corresponds to the deposition of a tape onto a flat support. In order that the feeding of the tape follows the roller kinematic, a guiding system has been modelled with shell elements as shown in Figure 6. This guiding system is a rigid part and the displacement of its centre of gravity is constrained by the displacement of the centre of the roller.

In the second phase, for stability consideration of the simulation, there is no compaction force applied to the roller. Instead, the normal displacement of the roller to the support is blocked (keeping the compaction force applied to the tape which was introduced during the first phase). In the same way, the tension is not applied to the tape in this second phase. Instead, the extremity of the tape follows a velocity $(V, 0, -V)$ (V being the velocity of the roller) in the local frame $(e1, e2, e3)$ of the roller ($e1$ being the main direction of the motion and $e3$ being the one normal to the support).

The complex kinematic of tape is described thanks to the kinematic of the roller associated to the contact interfaces between the parts: between the tape and the roller, between the tape and the support, and between the roller and the support.

One of the main difficulties is to apply the thermal boundary conditions onto regions which are not the same between two different times: the heating source (a laser for instance) is attached to the tool and moved while moving the tool. But as the tape reaches in front of the heating source, it is not the same portion of tape, which is facing at each instant. One of the solutions to that could be to pre-calculate the boundary conditions according to the supposed motion of the tape, and then create the associate time-function for each node on the tape. However, to retain solution at this stage of work is to create rigid surfaces that would follow the same motion than the roller, and on which the heating boundary conditions are applied. The heating flux is then transfer to the other parts by the mean of thermal contacts. For instance, on the Figure 6, a first surface has been created parallel to the support for the heating of the support. A heating flux or a process temperature is imposed on the surface of it and a thermal contact is created between the two parts. In the same way, a portion of the guide surface is used to heat the tape.

Last, thermal contact interfaces are defined between the various parts (tape/support, tape/roller, and roller/support) so that the heat flux can be exchanged between these parts.

Figure 6: Explicit thermo-mechanical model. Each tape deposit is decomposed in 2 phases: 1- a roller compaction / tape tensioning phase, then 2- the deposition with the tool kinematic

Figure 7: Temperature contour results obtained during the deposition of a second tape on the support – Explicit thermo-mechanical model. A temperature of 525K has been imposed to the heating zones.

3.1 Multi-laying of tapes

Successive depositions of tapes have been simulated, thanks to the multi-stage capability in ESI's Solution. The multi-stage feature can perform successive simulations. For each simulation stage, except the first, the results (displacement, temperature, stress...) of the previous simulation stage are used as initial conditions. In that way, multiple simulations with various loading stage can be easily chained. This multi-stage capability eases a lot the definition of the kinematics and the boundary conditions for each tape deposition.

At this stage of the work and once deposited, the tape displacement is assumed to be fixed for the next stages. Moreover, for each stage additional thermal contact have to be defined between the already deposited tapes and also with the other parts of the model (the new tap, the support, the roller if close enough...).

An example of temperature contour is shown in Figure 7, during the deposition of a second tape. A constant temperature of 525K has been imposed to the heating zones. It can be seen that the thermal contact between the support and the first tape able the partial heating of the tape during the deposition of the second one.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Two approaches to solve the thermo-mechanical problem of the ATL process have been proposed in this paper. These model have been model in a 3D frame, improving the usual 2D section models seen in literature.

The first one is a steady state model solved in an Eulerian frame attached to the tool, and which can take into account of the deformation of a soft roller. Contact pressure can be assessed from the mechanical analysis, but too high pressure are seen at the edge. It is probably due to too stiff tape behaviour in this early feasibility stage. Furthermore, the thermal problem is a diffusion-convection one and therefore a supplementary transfer term have been integrated to the differential equation. However, more works is needed to model more realistic boundary conditions imposed by the heating source and to integrate anisotropic thermal properties (for the steady state model only). Last, the resolution of this kind of model is quite fast, but is reduced to the cases where the velocity of the tool and the geometry of the part are constant during a large enough welding time.

For the case where these conditions are not fitted, a second Lagrangian thermo-mechanical model has been proposed, solved with an explicit scheme. This model can describe the tool kinematic and can simulate successive depositions of band. Due to explicit scheme and to punctual contact method,

scattering is observed in the contact pressure contours, while these contours can be well improved by filtering the results. In future works, focus will be made on more advanced contacts to improve this point. A work has also been done on the way to impose thermal boundary conditions to a system with a moving tool and a scrolling tape. The first results are encouraging, but again more works have to be done to integrate more realistic heating flux or temperature process imposed by the heating sources.

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REFERENCES

- [1] R. Schledjewski and M. Latrille, "Processing of unidirectional fiber reinforced tapes – fundamentals on the way to a process simulation tool (ProSimFRT)," *Composites Science and Technology*, vol. 63, pp. 2111-2118, 2003.
- [2] R. Schledjewski, "Thermoplastic tape placement process – in situ consolidation is reachable," *Plastics, Rubber and Composites*, vol. 38, no. 38, pp. 379-386, 2009.
- [3] C. NICODEAU, "Modelisation du soudage en continu de composites a matrice thermoplastique", Centre de Paris: Thèse, ENSAM, 20 septembre 2005.
- [4] W. Groupe, Weld strength of laser-assisted tape-placed thermoplastic composites, University of Twente, 2012.
- [5] M. Khan, P. Mitschang and R. Schledjewski, "Tracing the void content development and identification of its effecting parameters during in-situ consolidation of thermoplastic tape material," *Polymer and Polymer Composites*, vol. 18, no. 1, pp. 1-15, 2010.
- [6] M. Khan, P. Mitschang and R. Schledjewski, "Identification of some optimal process parameters to achieve higher laminate quality through tape placement," *Advances in Polymer Technology*, vol. 29, no. 2, pp. 98-111, 2010.
- [7] M. Khan, P. Mitschang and R. Schledjewski, "Parametric study on processing parameters and resulting part quality through thermoplastic tape placement process," *Journal of Composite Materials*, vol. 47, no. 4, pp. 485-499, 2003.
- [8] M. Narnhofer, R. Schledjewski and P. Mitschang, "Simulation of the tape-laying process for thermoplastic matrix composites," *Advances in Polymer Technology*, vol. 32, pp. 705-713, 2013.
- [9] J. Bergheau, V. Robin and F. Boitout, "Finite Element Simulation of Processes Involving Moving Heat Sources. Application to Welding and Surface Treatment.," *Journal of Shanghai Jiaotong University (Science)*, vol. 5, no. 1, pp. 114-122, 2000.
- [10] Y. Duplessis Kergomard, M. Perrin, A. Trameçon and P. De Luca, "Hybrid thermoplastic yarn to 3d complex shaped thermoplastic composite structure: simulation of braiding and subsequent consolidation" in *ECCM16*, Sevilla, 2014.
- [11] ESI GROUP, PAM-FORM 2G 2015 User's Guide, ESI GROUP, 2015.

- [12] F. Chinesta, A. Leygue, B. Bognet, C. Ghnatios, F. Poulhaon, F. Bordeu, A. Barasinski, A. Poitou, S. Chatel and S. Maison-Le-Poec, "First steps towards an advanced simulation of composites manufacturing by automated tape placement," *Int. J. Mater. From.*, vol. 7, no. 1, pp. 81-92, 2014.
- [13] ESI GROUP, SYSWORLD 2014, Technical Description of Capabilities, ESI GROUP, 2014.
- [14] L. Baillet, "Du mecanisme au contact modelisation par elements finis" in *Conférence CETIM*, 2000.
- [15] L. Baillet and T. Sassi, "Simulations numériques de différentes méthodes d'éléments finis pour les problèmes de contact avec frottement," *C.R. Mécanique*, vol. 331, pp. 789-796, 2003.
- [16] D. Chamoret, A. Rassineux and J. Bergheau, "A new smooth contact element: 3D diffuse contact element," *Int. J. Simul. Multidisci. Des. Optim.*, vol. 2, pp. 25-35, 2008.
- [17] F. O. Sonmez, H. T. Hahn and M. Akbulut, "Analysis of Process-Induced Residual Stresses in Tape Placement," *J. of Thermoplastic Composite Materials*, vol. 15, pp. 525-544, 2002.
- [18] N. Patel, V. Rohatgi and L. Lee, "Micro scale flow behavior and void formation mechanism during impregnation through a unidirectional slitched fiber glass mat.," *Polym. Eng. Sci.*, pp. 35(10):837-51, 1995.
- [19] A. Bensoussan, A. Lions and G. Papanicolaou, *Asymptotic analysis for periodic structures*, Amsterdam, 1978.
- [20] F. Phelan and G. Wise, "Analysis of transverse flow in aligned fibrous porous media.," *Compos part A*, vol. 27A, p. 25-34, 1996.
- [21] Y. Duan, Y. Vincent, F. Boitout, Leblond, J.B. and J. Bergheau, "Prediction of welding residual distortions of large structures using a local/global approach," *Journal of Mechanical Science and Technology*, vol. 21, no. 10, pp. 1700-1706, 2007.
- [22] ESI GROUP, FPM Incompressible: User's manual and basic validation test manual, ESI GROUP, 2006.
- [23] S. Tsirkas, P. Papanikos, K. Pericleous, N. Strusevich, F. Boitout and J. Bergheau, "Evaluation of distortions in laser welded shipbuilding parts using a local-global finite element approach," *Science and Technology of Welding and Joining*, vol. 8, no. 2, pp. 79-88, 2003.